

MASS-BEARING SPACE AND MATTER AS CONDENSED SPACE: A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON FUNDAMENTAL PHYSICS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, I propose a new conceptual framework in which space possesses mass, and matter is considered as highly condensed and localized regions of space. By attributing mass to space, I aim to provide alternative explanations for phenomena such as dark matter, dark energy, and cosmic expansion without invoking new, unobserved entities. I discuss the implications of this perspective on gravitational interactions, the nature of time and entropy, and particle creation from vacuum fluctuations. My hypothesis offers potential resolutions to current contradictions in physics and suggests new avenues for experimental validation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several concepts in physics present intuitive challenges. The notion of "nothing" is perplexing; if nothing exists, what occupies that space? Similarly, the idea of zero mass raises questions about the existence of such entities. Fundamental concepts such as fields, space, matter, mass, energy, time, charge, gravity, and particles are often treated as abstractions, yet only space and matter are directly observable. Moreover, space is often considered as "nothing," while matter comprises entities whose precise nature remains elusive. As we delve deeper, we find that atoms are predominantly empty space, and subatomic particles like electrons exhibit indeterminate positions and sizes.

Finite space is another challenging concept; if space is finite, what lies beyond its boundaries? Constructs like dark matter and dark energy have been introduced to reconcile discrepancies between theory and observation, yet they remain unobserved and may serve as placeholders in incomplete theories. The concept of singularities further complicates our understanding, potentially obscuring rather than clarifying fundamental physics.

In this paper, I present a new perspective that may address some of these issues. By considering space as having mass and matter as condensed space, I aim to reconcile certain contradictions in physics and provide alternative explanations for phenomena such as cosmic expansion and particle creation.

2. MOTIVATION

Current statements in physics (e.g., Caldwell & Kamionkowski, 2009; Riess *et al.*, 1998; Smolin, 2006) exhibit several contradictions:

- Matter and Space:** Matter, composed of standard model particles, exists and moves within space, yet the fundamental nature of both matter and space remains uncertain. What distinguishes matter from space?
- Massless Particles and Mass:** While matter has mass, space and some elementary particles are considered "massless." However, all physical objects in our observable world possess mass. Massless objects, such as photons, carry momentum (even though they are considered to have no mass). What exactly is mass?
- Gravitational Interactions:** Every object with mass participates in gravitational interactions, including massless photons and dark matter. In Newtonian gravitation, objects attract each other according to their masses.

- Dark Matter:** The observed mass of matter is insufficient to account for the gravitational binding of galaxies. Dark matter, comprising about 80% of the universe's mass, is hypothesized to explain this discrepancy, yet it remains undetected. What is dark matter?
- Dark Energy:** The universe's accelerated expansion is attributed to dark energy, an unobserved form of energy. However, the universe does not expand uniformly; local regions such as the Earth and the Milky Way remain stable in size. What is dark energy, and where does it originate?
- Conservation of Energy Paradox:** Dark energy poses a paradox concerning the conservation of energy. As space expands, the total amount of dark energy increases due to its constant density, seemingly violating conservation principles. Where does this additional energy come from?
- Quantum Field Theory (QFT):** QFT (e.g., Peskin, 2018; Weinberg, 1995) describes particles not as discrete spheres but as excitations of underlying fields that exist at every point in space. If fields and space are both fundamental and omnipresent, what distinguishes a field from space?

Furthermore, unresolved questions persist in physics, such as the unification of the four fundamental forces, the constancy and value of the speed of light, the nature of gravity, the behaviour of the Hubble constant, and the ultimate fate of cosmic expansion.

3. CONCEPT

I propose the following:

- Space with Mass:** Space possesses its own mass, which is not perceptible on local scales due to its extremely low density. Light also has mass in this framework. Therefore, both space and light can participate in gravitational interactions, consistent with predictions from relativity. No objects have zero mass; everything is involved in gravitational interactions. Fields are not separate entities; instead, space itself acts as both a medium and an object in physical interactions.
- Matter as Condensed Space:** Matter, including the stable elementary particles, is not distinct from space but is instead highly condensed and localized space. If we consider the space within our galaxy to have a density of $1.53 \times 10^{-16} \text{ g/m}^3$ (derived from galactic mass considerations), and a proton to have a density of $6.74 \times 10^{20} \text{ g/m}^3$, then a proton is more compressed than space by a factor of approximately 10^{36} . Interestingly, this factor aligns with the ratio of electromagnetic to gravitational forces, which may not be coincidental. Therefore, while atoms are often described as 99.99%

empty space, I contend that they are entirely composed of space, with protons being 10^{36} times denser and electrons approximately 10^{22} times denser than the surrounding space (though the precise size of the electron is uncertain).

4. IMPLICATIONS

- 1. Elimination of Dark Matter:** If space itself possesses mass equivalent to the so-called dark matter (Zwicky, 1933; Einasto, 2009), there is no need to invoke an unseen form of matter. Assuming the galaxy's dark matter mass is 5×10^{45} g, this mass can be attributed to space, thereby explaining the galaxy's gravitational cohesion. From this, I derive the space density of 1.53×10^{-16} g/m³.
- 2. Explanation of Cosmic Expansion Without Dark Energy:** The gravitational interactions between intergalactic space and galaxies can account for cosmic expansion without the need for dark energy (Peebles & Ratra, 2003, Perlmutter *et al.*, 1999). By considering the mass density of intergalactic space, the recession velocities of galaxies as described by Hubble's law can be explained without introducing additional factors.
- 3. Decreasing Hubble Constant:** My model allows for an explanation of cosmic expansion with acceleration described by the Hubble constant (Planck Collaboration, 2020), providing reasons for its observed decrease over time.
- 4. Reinterpretation of Quantum Field Theory Experiments:** By viewing matter as condensed space, I offer a new perspective on experiments involving particle creation from vacuum, aligning with observations without speculative constructs. Phenomena like Hawking radiation (e.g., Hawking, 1975; Frolov, 1990) and light creation from a vacuum (e.g., Wilson *et al.*, 2011) can be explained by fluctuations or reconfigurations in space's mass density.
- 5. Speed of Light and Space Density:** By correlating the densities of space and photons (with photon density being 6.13×10^{-7} g/m³ (Goray & Annavarapu, 2020), higher than space density by a factor of 10^9), it might be possible to deduce why the speed of light has its specific value, why it is finite, and why objects cannot exceed this speed. Since photons are the lightest particles, they are the fastest, but space itself can "expand" faster than light due to its lower density compared to light.
- 6. Curvature of Space-Time:** The curvature of space-time near massive objects (Einstein, 1916), as described in general relativity, may correspond to regions where space has greater density and mass.

5. HYPOTHESIS: COSMIC EXPANSION DUE TO SPACE STRETCHING

I hypothesize that the expansion of space between galaxies is driven by gravitational inhomogeneities. Near galaxies, the gravitational pull compresses space more strongly, while in less dense intergalactic voids, the gravitational pull is weaker. In these vast regions, the tidal effects caused by gravitational fields allow space to expand, analogous to spaghettification. This stretching of space leads to the observed cosmic expansion.

Since there is more space between us and distant galaxies, they recede from us at greater speeds than closer ones. This can be

conceptualized iteratively: the nearest 100 Mpc³ of space expands with velocity v , the next 100 Mpc³ (200 Mpc from us) also expands with velocity v , so objects twice as distant recede at speed $2v$, consistent with Hubble's law ($v=H_0D$).

As the universe expands, the density of space decreases because the volume increases. This implies that the gravitational influence of space itself diminishes over time, weakening the gravitational stretching between galaxies and reducing the rate of expansion per unit distance. Consequently, the Hubble constant decreases over time. Overall, while the universe's volume grows exponentially, each local region expands more slowly today than it did in the past.

6. SPECULATIVE HYPOTHESES

- **Mass and Charge:** Larger-scale masses appear only with charge; protons and electrons are much more massive than neutrinos, photons, or gravitons.
- **Superluminal Particles:** If a particle lighter than a photon ($<6.13 \times 10^{-7}$ g/m³) is created from the vacuum by compressing space, and its speed can be measured (e.g., in accelerators like the LHC), it may exceed the speed of light, even by a small amount.
- **Cosmic Expansion Limits:** Modelling cosmic expansion using our framework may provide insights into its temporal and spatial limits and enhance our understanding of its evolution.
- **Constant-Size Universe:** It is possible that reducing space density leads to increased distances or that decreased space density allows light to travel faster, causing the observed redshift to be a result of refraction rather than expansion. Thus, the universe might be of constant size.
- **Discrete Structure of Space:** The fundamental properties of space may only allow for stable particles like protons and electrons, while other forms of space densities (unstable particles like bosons or baryons) are unstable because the space structure does not support these densities.
- **Gravitational Force as Interaction with Space:** Gravitational force can be described as massive objects pulling on the fabric of space. Where the space volume (and mass) is large, space expands or changes its density distribution. Where the space mass is small compared to interacting objects, they pull each other toward the centre, using space as a medium.
- **Reassessment of the Big Bang Theory:** The universe may have started with space being evenly distributed in density and temperature, becoming more uneven over time (e.g., Penrose, 2010). The second law of thermodynamics, stating that entropy increases over time, could be interpreted as the distribution of space densities becoming more uneven.
- **Time as a Function of Space Density Distribution:** Time may be a proxy for the distribution of space densities (e.g., Essen & Parry, 1955). Time progresses as entropy grows, slowing down near massive objects and behaving unpredictably near singularities like black holes.

7. EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE

Currently, this concept does not directly conflict with established theories in physics, except perhaps those lacking

empirical evidence (e.g., dark energy, dark matter). However, direct empirical evidence supporting or refuting this concept is not clear, and as a non-physicist, my understanding is limited.

To test or falsify this concept, several scenarios could be considered:

a) **Detection of Dark Matter or Dark Energy:** If dark matter or dark energy are empirically detected and confirmed, this would challenge the concept.

b) **Existence of Negative Mass:** If negative mass is confirmed to exist, implying the possibility of zero mass, the idea that all objects have non-zero mass would be invalidated.

c) **Discovery of Stable Massive Particles Without Charge:** If stable massive particles with no charge are found to exist outside the nucleus, the idea that mass arises from charge would be questioned.

d) **Contradictions with Quantum Physics:** If the hypothesis directly contradicts observations in quantum physics, it would need to be reconsidered.

e) **Particle Creation from Vacuum:** Conversely, if a new particle is formed directly from the vacuum, it may support the views on the nature and structure of particles and space.

f) **Superluminal Particles:** If such a particle is lighter than a photon and exceeds the speed of light, or at least matches it, it would strongly support the concept.

g) **Accurate Prediction of Hubble Constant Decrease:** If a cosmic expansion model based on this concept accurately predicts the observed decrease in the Hubble constant, it would provide significant support.

h) **Evidence of Discrete Space and Mass-Bearing Space:** If space is found to be discrete and measurable, if large amounts of space are empirically shown to have mass, or if the speed of light is theoretically modelled to not exceed c due to gravity, these findings would support the concept.

8. CONCLUSION

I have proposed a new perspective on fundamental physics by attributing mass to space and considering matter as condensed space. This framework offers potential explanations for phenomena such as dark matter, dark energy, cosmic expansion, and particle creation without invoking unobserved entities. By reinterpreting gravitational interactions, the nature

of time and entropy, and the structure of particles, I aim to address contradictions in current physics and stimulate new avenues for theoretical and experimental exploration. Further research and empirical testing are necessary to validate or refute this concept, and I hope it may contribute to a deeper understanding of the universe.

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